

ESTIMATION OF BISMUTH. PART VI. COLORIMETRIC ANALYSIS WITH PHENYLDITHIOBIAZOLONE THIOL

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Bismuth has been estimated both colorimetrically and gravimetrically with the reagent phenyldithiobiazolone thiol. Maximum absorption of the colour system has been found to be at 460 m μ . The colour system has been found to obey Beer's law through a long range of concentration of bismuth. Effect of diverse ions has also been studied.

Like dimercaptothiobiazole, the reagent phenyldithiobiazolone thiol (C₈H₆N₂S₃) having the reacting group RN-CS-S-C-(SH)-N, has been found to give coloured precipitates with the metals of the sulphide group. It gives yellow precipitates with gold, mercury, lead, silver, platinum, arsenic and antimony, white with cadmium and zinc, brown with copper, brick red with tin and red with bismuth and palladium.

Dubsky and Trtilek (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1934, 96, 412) used this reagent for the detection of small quantities of bismuth, their identification limit being 1.2 μ g. and sensitivity 1 part in 28,000 parts. Air dried bismuth salt of the reagent were found by them to be of composition Bi(C₈H₅N₂S₃)₃, 2H₂O, which when heated in air at 100° loses 3.09% of water.

The author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 396) however, has observed that the coloration limit can be extended to 1 part in 6000,000 parts if nitric acid solution is used and not chloride solution as used by Dubsky and others (*loc. cit.*) and that bismuth to the extent of 3 γ in 20 c.c. solution can be accurately estimated colorimetrically with this reagent as the colour system obeys Beer's law through a long range of concentration studied. Further, phenyldithiobiazolone thiol is found to be a suitable reagent for the gravimetric estimation of bismuth as the bismuth compound of the reagent is stable and of definite composition. The air dried compound on heating to 105° has been found to lose only 2.94% of water even on heating for several hours. No further loss in weight was observed on heating this up to 130°. This suggests that the bismuth compound, which was heated at 105°, is of composition Bi(C₈H₅N₂S₃)₃, $\frac{1}{2}$ H₂O.

With the help of a Dubosq colorimeter, bismuth has been estimated colorimetrically and also the effect of diverse ions on the colour system has been studied.

With a spectrophotometer the peak of the absorption band of the colour system has been found to be at 460 m μ and that it obeys Beer's law has further been verified by the fact that a straight line resulted when the logarithms of the transmittances at 460 m μ has been plotted against the respective concentrations.

Effect of organic solvents on the compounds, formed by the reagent with the metals of the sulphide group, has also been examined with the idea of separating bismuth from other elements.

Reagents.—Reagents that were used during these experiments were the same as used during the colorimetric analysis of bismuth with dimer captothiobiazole (Part IV of this series).

Phenyldithiobiazolone thiol ($C_8H_6N_2S_3$) was prepared as potassium salt (m.p. 250°) and recrystallised (Busch, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2511). This was kept in an orange coloured desiccator. A 0.5 per cent solution of potassium salt of the reagent in water was prepared. This solution was colourless but on keeping for several days, a slight opalescence was observed.

EXPERIMENTAL

With dimercaptothiobiazole (*loc. cit.*), nitric acid, up to a certain limit (5 c.c. normal nitric acid in a volume of 20 c.c.), has been found to intensify the colour. But here no influence of nitric acid on the colour system has been observed, even when one c.c. of concentrated nitric acid (65%) in a volume of 20 c.c. was present. Like dimercaptothiobiazole, an excess of the reagent solution of gum acacia has no influence on the colour system.

During the colorimetric estimation of bismuth by the reagent phenyldithiobiazolone thiol it has been observed that if the amount of bismuth is less than 3.5×10^{-4} g. solution of gum acacia need not be used. But for bismuth of higher amount, gum acacia solution should be used to stabilise the colloidal suspension of the compound formed with the reagent. With this reagent full development of maximum colour intensity takes place in a minute or two.

General Procedure

In the tube of a Dubosq colorimeter were taken a few c.c. of the bismuth nitrate solution containing some free nitric acid to keep the bismuth in solution, one c.c. of gum acacia solution, a few c.c. of water and then a few drops of the reagent solution (about 1 c.c.), drop by drop, with shaking, till no further development of colour was noticed. The volume of the solution was maintained at 20 c.c. After thorough mixing the colour was compared. If the bismuth solution contains ions other than nitrate, 5 c.c. of normal nitric acid should be added to the solution along with 5 c.c. of gum acacia solution. Results are given below.

Bi taken.	Bi found.	Error.	Bi taken	Bi found.	Error.
8.48 mg.	8.46 mg.	-0.02 mg.	0.259 mg.	0.256 mg.	-0.003
3.886	3.920	+0.032	0.1037	0.1037	Nil
2.592	2.580	-0.012	0.065	0.066	+0.001
1.296	1.30	+0.004	0.065	0.065	Nil
0.518	0.524	+0.006	0.039	0.040	+0.001

For the estimation of one milligram of bismuth or more, one should take the nitric acid solution of bismuth in a 100 c.c. volumetric flask, add a few c.c. of gum acacia solution sufficient to stabilise the colloidal suspension, dilute with water almost

to the mark, add a few c.c. of the reagent solution till there is no further increase in colour and then make up to the mark with water and mix thoroughly. 20 C.c. of this solution are then taken in the colorimeter tube and the colour compared. The same quantities of nitric acid, reagent and gum acacia are added to both the unknown and the standard.

Conformity to Beer's law.—That the colour system obeys Beer's law through a long range of concentration is evident from the graphs (Figs. 1 and 2) drawn by plotting the reciprocal colorimetric readings on the abscissa and the concentrations on the ordinates.

Stability of the colour.—As with dimercaptothiobiazole (*loc. cit.*) here also glycerine or agar agar can be used as stabilisers in addition to gum acacia. Gelatine cannot be used as such, as it gives a similar cream coloured precipitate.

The stability of the colour system depends upon the amount of nitric acid and on the amount of bismuth present in exactly the same way as has been observed with dimercaptothiobiazole. But here if the amount of bismuth is less than 3.5×10^{-4} g. it can be estimated without the addition of gum acacia.

Interference.—The effect of diverse ions on the colour system has been studied, in the same way as has been done with dimercaptothiobiazole, with the standard solutions of the ions prepared from the chloride, nitrate or sulphate salts of the cations and from sodium or potassium salts of the anions. Interference of the ions has been determined under the conditions recommended under the general procedure, using bismuth concentration of 0.26 milligram and adding 5 c.c. of normal nitric acid along with 5 c.c. of gum accia to the solution. The effect of nitrate ions was studied by adding only 5 c.c. of gum acacia to the bismuth nitrate solution containing very small quantity of free nitric acid (dilute).

The limiting concentrations of the coloured ions, that interfere only if present at concentrations exceeding that required to produce the colour due to the ion itself, are: Cu^{++} , 0.07 mg.; Co^{++} , 2 mg.; Ni^{++} , 9 mg.

The following ions are without effect even at a concentration of: Mn^{++} , 100 mg.; Fe^{++} , 100 mg.; NO_3^- , 100 mg.; 1 c.c. HNO_3 (sp. gr. 1.4); SO_4^{--} , 100 mg.; $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{--}$, 100 mg.; $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6^{--}$, 100 mg.; 10 c.c. H_2SO_3 (saturated solution); 1 c.c. H_3PO_2 (*d.* 1.274).

The limiting concentrations for the interfering ions due to precipitations are: Zn^{++} , 10 mg.; Cd^{++} , 0.5 mg.; Pb^{++} , 1 mg.; Hg^{++} , 0.5 mg.; Ag^{+} , 0.3 mg.; Cl^- , 50 mg.; As^{+++} , 0.05 mg.; Sb^{+++} , 0.1 mg.; Sn^{++} , 0.2 mg. The concentrations of the interfering ions can be further increased if the concentrations of nitric acid is increased. Thus in presence of phosphate or other ions that form insoluble salts with bismuth, it can be estimated if the precipitate formed is first dissolved in nitric acid. As for example, with 100 mg. of phosphate ions, it has been estimated in presence of 1 c.c. concentrated nitric acid (*d.* 1.4) in a volume of 20 c.c.

Estimation of Bismuth in presence of other ions.—For the estimation of small quantities of bismuth in presence of other interfering ions, it was precipitated as phenyl arsonate (Part IV of this series). From this precipitate bismuth was estimated

in the same way as has been done with dimercaptiothiazazole (Part V of this series) and the results obtained thereby are given below.

Bi taken.	Bi found.	Error.
0.088 mg.	0.087 mg.	-0.001 mg.
0.019	0.049	Nil.
0.0286	0.0292	-0.0008

Solubility of the Salts formed by the metals with the Reagent in Organic solvents.—The bismuth compound is soluble in alcohols such as ethyl, methyl, normal and isopropyl and isoamyl; and also in ether, chloroform, acetone, pyridine and in ethyl acetate; sparingly soluble in carbon disulphide and insoluble in carbon tetrachloride and in benzene. Compounds formed with copper, cadmium, lead, mercury (ic), antimony and silver are insoluble in ether, isoamyl alcohol and in chloroform; compound of cobalt is insoluble in ether and in chloroform but soluble in isoamyl alcohol, that of tin (ous) is insoluble in ether, but soluble in isoamyl alcohol and in chloroform and that of zinc is soluble in ether, but insoluble in chloroform and in isoamyl alcohol.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

Spectrophotometric Study.—Spectrophotometric studies were undertaken with the same instruments and in the same way as with dimercaptiothiazazole (*loc. cit.*). The solution that was used for this contained in a volume of 20 c.c. 0.35 mg. of bismuth nitrate, a little quantity of free nitric acid to keep the bismuth in solution and 2 c.c. of the reagent. When the logarithms of the observed transmittances were plotted against the wave-lengths, peak of the absorption band was found to be at 460m μ (Fig. 1). The reagent solution or the solution of gum acacia had no absorption in the visible region.

Beer's law.—That the colour system also obeys Beer's law has further been verified by plotting the logarithms of the observed transmittances at 460m μ , for a

number of solutions containing from 65 p.p.m. of bismuth, against the respective concentrations (Fig. 2).

As bismuth has been found to be quantitatively precipitated with this reagent from a dilute nitric acid solution containing about 10 c.c. of normal nitric acid per 100 c.c. and the compound formed is stable and of constant composition, a few determinations of bismuth gravimetrically has been undertaken in the following way and thereby good results have been obtained.

To a nitrate solution of bismuth containing 10 c.c. of free nitric acid (normal) per 100 c.c., is added with stirring a few c.c. of one per cent solution of the potassium salt of the reagent in water till no further precipitation takes place. The solution is then heated for some time with stirring till the precipitates coagulate and the solution becomes clear. This is then quickly filtered hot through a porcelain gooch crucible, washed with hot water, dried at 100° and weighed. The weight of the bismuth compound is then multiplied by the factor 0.2340 as the percentage of bismuth in the compound $(C_8H_5N_2S_3)_3 Bi, \frac{1}{2}H_2O$ is only 23.4.

Bi taken	Bi found	Bi taken	Bi found
0.0362 g	0.0363 g.	0.0181	0.0180
0.0543	0.0545		

Other elements such as zinc, cadmium, palladium, mercury (ic), lead etc., are quantitatively precipitated by the reagent and further with traces of palladium a red coloration is obtained.

Further works, on the estimation and separation of bismuth from other elements gravimetrically and colorimetrically by extracting with organic solvents as also the estimations of other elements by this reagent are in progress.

My best thanks are due to Prof. P. Rây and to Prof. J. N. Mukherjee for the facilities received in working out this piece of work in their laboratories.

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Received July 8, 1944